

A volunteer review of "Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories"

Rebeca Rimniceanu

February 12, 2025

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It's more essential than ever for us, as inhabitants of this planet, to educate ourselves about environmental issues. That's why "Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories" by Quan-Hoang Vuong and Minh-Hoang Nguyen is a must-read.

This book addresses a wide range of pressing topics—climate change, deforestation, biodiversity loss, and natural disasters, to name just a few.

It offers a thoughtful study of how quantum and information theories can drive a much-needed change in economics. The authors challenge the traditional, anthropocentric perspective of economics, advocating instead for integrating physics principles and taking into consideration the crisis facing our planet.

The writing is dense and filled with valuable information. At times, I found it challenging to grasp every concept and term, but the authors did a good job of explaining complex ideas.

As I read on, I often felt a sense of dread when faced with current issues like the 2-degree Celsius temperature rise, the U.S. withdrawal from the Paris Agreement, and President Donald Trump's encouragement to drill for oil, which will further increase greenhouse gas emissions.

I disagreed with the authors when they suggested some activists harm the movement's reputation through their aggressive tactics. This led me to question who will drive the significant changes needed for our society. Will it be elected officials, many of whom deny climate change? Or companies that engage in greenwashing? Or is it millionaires who abuse their power? Although alienating support is unhelpful, I doubt a controversial Greta Thunberg tweet from a few years ago is the main reason people don't take climate activism seriously.

The future of our existence hinges on the decisions made by our leaders and their greed. This read is an insightful exploration for anyone interested in understanding the complexities of economics and their role in human sustainability.

Even though the book was a bit challenging and I had some different viewpoints from the authors, I found it to be a significant read. Therefore, I rate it 4 out of 5 stars.

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by Rebeca Rimniceanu » 12 Feb 2025, 13:35

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Screenshot. A volunteer review of “*Better Economics for the Earth*” by Rebeca Rimniceanu on Februar 12, 2025 [1].

(*) Note: This paper reprints Rimniceanu’s volunteer review [1] appearing on Online Book Club of the title [2].

References

- [1] Rimnicean, R. (2025, Feb. 12). Review of Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories. <https://forums.onlinebookclub.org/viewtopic.php?f=114&t=617168>
- [2] Vuong, Q. H. & Nguyen, M. H. (2024). *Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0D98L5K44>